

TECHNOLOGY OF LEVEL DIFFERENTIATION IN THE STUDY OF I.S. TURGENEV'S NOVEL "FATHERS AND CHILDREN"

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Keywords: differentiation, student-centered learning, mental development of the individual, groups of students, perception, analysis.

In order for training to be considered student-centered and most effective, it should focus on:

- the level of training in the given field of knowledge, the level of general development, culture;
- features of the mental development of the individual (features of memory, thinking, perception, the ability to manage and regulate one's emotional sphere, etc.);
- features of character, temperament.

Therefore, training should be essentially differentiated.

We are talking about creating groups of different levels - A, B, C. The guys continue to study in their classes, but they go to lessons in individual subjects in their own groups - some in group A, some in group B, some in group C .

The problem of studying the novel by I.S. Turgenev "Fathers and Sons" was touched upon in other works by the author of this article, but the aspect of level differentiation was not touched upon in them.

So, when studying the novel "Fathers and Sons", students of the 1st group can be asked to answer the following questions in the form of cards (the material of the entire novel is divided into these questions, more precisely, its key moments).

The shorter the question, the more actively this group will participate in the discussion and the more effective the result will be).

Pupils of the 2nd group can be offered the creative task "Comic in the novel" "Fathers and Sons". They look for relevant episodes in the text of the novel.

In addition, students of this group can be offered a mini-quiz "Guess the hero". The element of competition in such cases further develops the desire of students and their interest in the text of the novel.

Here, unlike the 1st group, students will need a more in-depth knowledge of the material.

Finally, for students of the 3rd group, as more prepared, it is advisable to ask the essay "My opinion about Bazarov" (or on another topic). By setting an essay before the final lesson, the teacher does not constrain the independent judgments of students, provides them with the opportunity to freely express their point of view.

The teacher directs the work on the essay, indicates how to work on the proposed topic.

The main requirements for an essay on the topic "My opinion about Bazarov" are as follows: the student expresses his personal attitude towards the hero of the novel, even if it does not coincide with the teacher's point of view, but this opinion must be substantiated, argued, broadly using the text of the novel and historical and literary facts known to the student. It is impossible to reduce the essay to a characterization of the hero, to a list of his traits. One should not strive for an exhaustive analysis of Bazarov's qualities, all his advantages and disadvantages.

A student may become interested in one feature of the hero (the directness and honesty of his nature, the ability for great deep love, etc.) and stop in the essay only on this feature. No matter how emotionally, directly and sincerely the student expresses his thoughts and feelings, the composition requires logical harmony, clarity of composition. It needs to be written according to plan. The teacher does not give a ready-made composition

plan (there can be no standard), but offers several sample questions. These questions are not recorded. The purpose of these questions is to guide students' thoughts.

During the discussion of the essays, it is clarified to what extent the students completed the task. Homework: work on mistakes in essays. This refers to grammatical, stylistic, content errors, as well as non-compliance with the requirements for writing.

Students are invited to redo the essay if these requirements are not met, and if it expresses the wrong point of view (for example, a sharp condemnation of Bazarov). Recycling is possible provided that the student has revised his beliefs and abandoned the wrong point of view.

References:

1. Rahimova M.E., Bogdanovich G.A. (2021), Ispol'zovanie priyoma «Sinkvejn» pri izuchenii romana I.S.Turgeneva «Otcy i deti» (Using the "Siquain" technique in the study of I.S. Turgenev's novel "Fathers and Sons"). «YAzyki i literatura v polikul'turnom prostranstve». Materialy Mezhdunarodnoj nauchno-prakticheskoy konferencii, ("Languages and Literature in a Multicultural Space". Proceedings of the International Scientific and Practical Conference), Andijan, 2021, p. 311-315.
2. Rahimova M.E., Bogdanovich G.A. (2021), Ispol'zovanie priyoma «Diamanta» pri izuchenii romana I.S.Turgeneva «Otcy i deti». (Using the technique of "Diamond" in the study of the novel by I.S. Turgenev "Fathers and Sons"). «Nauka i obrazovanie – vazhnyj faktor razvitiya strany». Materialy Respublikanskoj nauchno-prakticheskoy konferencii, posvyashchyonnoj 90-letiyu Andizhanskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta imeni Z.M.Babura. ("Science and education are an important factor in the development of the country." Materials of the Republican scientific-practical conference dedicated to the 90th anniversary of Andijan State University named after Z. M. Babur). Andijan, 2021, p. 73-75
3. Rahimova M.E. (2021), Ispol'zovanie tekhniki «Pinbord» pri izuchenii romana I.S.Turgeneva «Otcy i deti».(The use of the "Pinboard" technique in the study of I.S. Turgenev's novel "Fathers and Sons").

«YAzyk – literatura – kul'tura». Materialy Mezhdunarodnoj nauchno-prakticheskoy konferencii ("Language - Literature - Culture". Proceedings of the International Scientific and Practical Conference), Moscow, 2022, p. 343-345

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